

CREEP AND STRESS RELAXATION OF ANGLE-PLY CFRP LAMINATES AT HIGH TEMPERATURE AND NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

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SUMMARY: Creep and stress relaxation behaviors of symmetric angle-ply CFRP laminates at relatively high stress/strain levels and at high temperature are examined. Creep and stress relaxation tests are performed at 100°C for five hours on plain coupon specimens. For each specimen, the creep and stress relaxation tests are carried out at three different stress/strain levels. Simulations of creep and stress relaxation for the angle-ply laminates are performed using the classical laminated plate theory and a phenomenological viscoplasticity model for individual plies. Material constants of the ply viscoplasticity model are identified on the basis of the off-axis creep behavior for unidirectional laminate. Excellent agreements between the predicted and observed results for the instantaneous elastoviscoplastic and subsequent creep or stress relaxation behaviors are achieved by taking into account the deformation-induced fiber rotation. The present results also confirm that the stress relaxation behavior is consistent with the creep behavior of the same type of composite system.

KEYWORDS: creep, stress relaxation, viscoplasticity model, angle-ply laminates, high stress, high temperature, carbon/epoxy

INTRODUCTION

A strong tendency of polymers for viscoplastic behavior at a relatively high stress/strain has a significant influence on the mechanical behavior of polymer matrix composites (PMCs), especially when they are subjected to off-axis load. To high-temperature durability of PMC laminates for advanced aerospace structures, in particular, the matrix-dominated response to shear loading is crucial [1]. For evaluating the performance and reliability of PMC laminates, therefore, it is very important to accumulate fundamental data on the time- and rate-dependent behavior under various loading and temperature conditions. Systematic information on the time-dependent behavior of PMC laminates with basic configuration is also of great significance to establish constitutive models for reliable design analyses of high-temperature composite structures.

The time- and rate-dependent behavior of PMC laminates can be manifested typically by the strain-rate effects on stress-strain curves, creep behavior at a constant stress and stress relaxation behavior at a constant strain. The rate-dependence of initial slope of the stress-strain curve was observed for off-axis specimens of unidirectional PMCs [2]. The strain-rate dependence of the off-axis tensile flow stress in the nonlinear regime was studied by Yoon and Sun [3] for unidirectional carbon/PEEK system. The tensile creep behavior was reported for the angle-ply laminates made of carbon/PEEK [4] and Glass/Epoxy [5]. Kawai [6] conducted the off-axis tensile creep tests on unidirectional T800H/Epoxy laminate subjected to a single step change in stress, and elucidated the effect of load history on the off-axis creep behavior through comparisons with the creep behavior under constant stress conditions. Nevertheless, systematic data for creep and stress relaxation behaviors of unidirectional and multidirectional PMC laminates over a wide range of stress/strain levels are still limited. In particular, history effects on the time-dependent behavior of PMCs at relatively high stress/strain levels as well as at high temperatures have not been sufficiently elucidated. Very few studies are reported especially regarding the stress relaxation effects in unidirectional and multidirectional laminates.

In the range of relatively small stress or strain, the time-dependent behavior of PMCs is characterized

by linear and nonlinear viscoelastic responses of polymer matrices. At a relatively high stress/strain level, however, the time-dependent behavior of polymers tends to deviate from the predictions using viscoelasticity models. To account for the time-dependent inelastic behavior of PMCs, macroscopic viscoplasticity modeling [7, 8] on the basis of the concept of overstress is attempted for engineering purposes. On the application of a viscoplasticity model, however, very few studies have been reported for the creep and stress relaxation behaviors of unidirectional and multidirectional PMC laminates at high stress/strain levels and at high temperatures. Regarding the validity of the viscoplasticity models for describing the time-dependent inelastic behavior of PMCs under those conditions, therefore, we need further studies.

The aim of this study is twofold. First, characteristics of the creep and stress relaxation behaviors of symmetric angle-ply carbon/epoxy laminates exposed to elevated temperature are examined at relatively high stress/strain levels. Second, creep and stress relaxation simulations of the symmetric angle-ply laminates are carried out by using the classical lamination theory and by assuming a viscoplasticity model for individual plies. Material constants involved by the ply viscoplasticity model are identified on the basis of the off-axis creep behavior of unidirectional laminates. In the simulations, effects of fiber rotation induced by deformation are considered. Validity of the simple CLT-based method for describing the time-dependent inelastic behavior is evaluated on the basis of the experimental results obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Specimens

Unidirectional laminates $[0]_{12}$ and angle-ply laminates $[\pm 30]_{3s}$, $[\pm 45]_{3s}$ and $[\pm 60]_{3s}$ are fabricated from the prepreg (P2212-15, TORAY) which consists of the carbon fiber (T800H) and the thermosetting epoxy resin (#3631). These laminates were cured in an autoclave at 180°C for two hours. The glass transition temperature of the epoxy resin is 215°C . Plain coupon specimens were used. The shape and dimensions of the specimens are based on the testing standards JIS K7073 and ASTM D3039; the specimen length $L = 200$ mm, the gauge length $L_G = 100$ mm, the thickness $t = 1.7 \sim 2$ mm, respectively. The width is specified to be $w = 20$ mm except the 0° specimens ($w = 10$ mm) of the unidirectional laminate. Rectangular-shaped aluminum-alloy tabs were attached on both ends of the specimens using epoxy adhesive.

Test Procedure

Constant-stress creep and constant-strain relaxation tests were carried out at 100°C for five hours. Three different stress/strain levels were selected for each specimen; the middle level was specified to be the value at 60 percent of the static tensile strength. The creep and stress relaxation tests were performed using a servo-hydraulic MTS-810 testing machine. To raise the temperature of specimens, a heating chamber with a precise digital control capability was employed. The loading to the stress/strain kept constant was controlled in a constant stroke rate of 1.0 mm/min. The specimens were heated up to 100°C in air without applying the load, and they were preconditioned in the test environment for 60 minutes prior to test. The variation of specimen temperature in time from the prescribed value was less than 1.0°C .

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Creep Behavior

Creep curves for the angle-ply laminates ($[\pm 30]_{3s}$ and $[\pm 60]_{3s}$) are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, respectively. The creep behavior of the angle-ply laminates is clearly observed, regardless of the fiber

Fig. 1 Creep curves for the $[\pm 30]_{3S}$ laminate

Fig. 2 Creep curves for the $[\pm 60]_{3S}$ laminate

Fig. 3 Creep strain recovery for the $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ laminate

orientations. For the given fiber orientation, the creep strain becomes larger at a higher creep stress level. The creep rate rapidly decreases with time in an early stage of the creep response, and it tends to vanish, regardless of the sustained stress level and of the fiber orientation. The transient response is thus dominant for the creep behavior of the angle-ply laminates at 100°C.

Creep strain recovery behavior of the angle-ply laminate $[\pm 45]_{3S}$ following the prior constant

stress creep response is shown in Fig. 3. The creep strain recovery rapidly takes place just after the stress removal. Subsequently, the rate of creep strain recovery decreases to vanish. The amount of creep strain recovery is as small as about 24 to 55 percent of the prior creep strain. A very small rate of the creep strain recovery at the end of the duration implies that a part of the prior creep strain eventually remains regardless of the creep stress level and of the ply orientation. The same tendency was found for the same type of unidirectional laminates [6]. These observations imply that the high-temperature creep behavior of the unidirectional and angle-ply laminates at a relatively high stress level has a nature of viscoplasticity. Note that an incomplete creep strain recovery is consistent with other facts that a permanent deformation remains after unloading and the creep compliance depends on the applied stress.

Fig. 4 Stress relaxation curves for the $[\pm 30]_{3S}$ laminate

Fig. 5 Stress relaxation curves for the $[\pm 60]_{3S}$ laminate

Stress Relaxation Behavior

Stress relaxation behavior of the $[\pm 30]_{3S}$ and $[\pm 60]_{3S}$ laminates is shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, respectively. The stress relaxation effect is clearly observed. The amount of stress relaxation depends on the total strain kept constant, and it becomes more significant at a larger strain level. Just after the total strain is kept constant, the longitudinal stress rapidly relaxes and then tends to approach a steady-state value associated with the strain imposed. As the stress relaxation response approaches the steady state, the time rate of stress relaxation rapidly decreases to vanish, regardless of the sustained strain and of the fiber orientation. This indicates that the creep response of the epoxy matrix almost terminates in a short time. It has been additionally observed that the relaxation modulus depends on the strain sustained.

MODELING AND SIMULATION

Phenomenological Viscoplasticity Model

In the overstress-based viscoplasticity formulation for the time-dependent inelastic behavior of PMCs, the master relationship between the effective viscoplastic strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_{eff}^p$ and the effective overstress H is written in the form

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{eff}^p = \langle H / K \rangle^{1/m} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 6 Predicted creep curves for the $[\pm 30]_{3S}$ laminate

Fig. 7 Predicted creep curves for the $[\pm 60]_{3S}$ laminate

where $H = \sigma_{eff} - r - r_0$. The effective overstress stands for a part of the applied stress over a scalar internal variable r ; the viscoplastic strain rate disappears when the external stress is lower than the level of $r + r_0$. The parameter r_0 prescribes a size of initial elastic domain, and it may be treated as an initial value of r . The angular brackets in Eq. (1) denote the operation: $\langle x \rangle = x$ ($x \geq 0$); $\langle x \rangle = 0$ ($x < 0$). The symbols K and m represent constants for the given material. The viscoplasticity model is characterized by the evolution equation of the isotropic hardening variable r . In the present study, we assume the following expression:

$$r = \sum_i r_i = \sum_i b_i (Q_i - r_i) \dot{\epsilon}_{eff}^p \quad (2)$$

where Q_i stands for the saturated value of r_i , and a material constant b_i characterizes the manner in which r_i approaches the saturated value. The multi-component representation of the evolution equation of r , Eq. (2), in the viscoplasticity model provides excellent flexibility in describing the nonlinear response of individual plies. The material constants involved by the viscoplasticity model are determined on the basis of the off-axis creep behavior of unidirectional laminate.

Simulation Results

The time-dependent behavior of the angle-ply laminates has been simulated using the classical lamination theory and the viscoplasticity model for plies. Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 display comparisons between the predicted and observed creep behavior for the angle-ply laminates $[\pm 30]_{3S}$ and $[\pm 60]_{3S}$, respectively. In the simulation, the deformation-induced fiber rotation [9, 10] is considered. The total

Fig. 8 Predicted stress relaxation curves for the $[\pm 30]_{3S}$ laminate

Fig. 9 Predicted stress relaxation curves for the $[\pm 60]_{3S}$ laminate

strain is taken in the vertical axis of these figures, since the whole process composed of the prior constant-rate straining to a stress level and the subsequent stress holding is simulated. It is seen that the predicted creep curves are in good agreement with the experimental results. This indicates that the laminate viscoplasticity model succeeds in accurately predicting the creep behavior at a constant stress as well as the instantaneous elastoviscoplastic strain associated with the initial loading to the creep stress level.

Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 present comparisons between the predicted and observed stress relaxation behavior of the $[\pm 30]_{3S}$ and $[\pm 60]_{3S}$ laminates, respectively. In the stress relaxation simulation, effects of the local strain recovery as well as the fiber rotation were considered. These figures show that the laminate viscoplasticity model provides fairly good predictions for the stress relaxation behavior of the angle-ply laminates. Since the material constants of the ply viscoplasticity model were identified on the basis of the off-axis creep behavior, we can confirm that the stress relaxation behavior is consistent with the creep behavior of the same composite system.

CONCLUSIONS

High-temperature creep and stress relaxation behaviors of unidirectional and angle-ply T800H/3631 laminates at relatively high stress/strain levels were elucidated. Creep and stress relaxation simulations were performed using the classical laminated plate theory and a phenomenological viscoplasticity model for individual plies. In the simulation of angle-ply laminates, effects of fiber rotation as well as local strain recovery were considered. Excellent agreements between the predicted and observed results are achieved for the instantaneous elastoviscoplastic and the subsequent creep or stress-relaxation behavior. It may be thus concluded that the phenomenological laminate model based on the classical lamination theory and the ply viscoplasticity model has a capability to describe the creep and stress relaxation behaviors as well as the instantaneous elastoviscoplastic behavior for the angle-ply laminates. The successful application of the laminate viscoplasticity model also confirms that the stress relaxation behavior is consistent with the creep behavior for the same composite system.

REFERENCES

1. W.H. Morita and S.R. Graves, "Graphite/polyimide technology overview and space shuttle orbiter applications," *In: Proc. of 14th National SAMPE Technical Conference*, October, 387-401 (1982).
2. M. Kawai, Y. Masuko, Y. Kawase and R. Negishi, "Micromechanical analysis of the off-axis rate-dependent inelastic behavior of unidirectional AS4/PEEK at high temperature," *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, 43(3): 2069-2090 (2000).
3. K.J. Yoon and C.T. Sun, "Characterization of elastic-viscoplastic properties of an AS4/PEEK thermoplastic composite," *Journal of Composite Materials*, 25: 1277-1296 (1991).
4. S.K. Ha and G.S. Springer, "Time dependent behavior of laminated composite at elevated temperature," *Journal of Composite Materials*, 23: 1159-1197 (1989).
5. S.W. Beckwith, "Creep evaluation of a Glass/Epoxy composite," *SAMPE Quarterly*, 8-15 (1980).
6. M. Kawai, "Off-axis creep behavior of unidirectional polymer matrix composites at high temperature," *In: Proc. of UTAM Symposium on Creep in Structures*, 469-478 (2001).
7. T.S. Gates and C.T. Sun, "Elastic/viscoplastic constitutive model for fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites," *AIAA Journal*, 29(3): 457-463 (1991).
8. C. Wang and C.T. Sun, "Experimental characterization of constitutive models for PEEK thermoplastic composite at heating stage during forming," *Journal of Composite Materials*, 31(15): 1480-1506 (1997).
9. C.T. Sun and C. Zhu, "The effect of deformation-induced change of fiber orientation on the non-linear behavior of polymeric composite laminates," *Composites Science and Technology*, 60: 2337-2345 (2000).
10. C.T. Herakovich, R.D. Schroedter III, A. Grasser and L. Guitard, "Damage evolution in $[\pm 45]_s$ laminates with fiber rotation," *Composites Science and Technology*, 60: 2781-2789 (2000).